

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE ASSOCIATION OF POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION WITH SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEMOGRAPHICS

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Abstract

Background: Postpartum depression is mental health disorder that affects on mother's health. That start immediately after delivery up to 6 weeks (42 days) but some studies extend up to 12 month after delivery.

Objective: To estimate the prevalence of postpartum depression among mothers within six weeks of postpartum and to identify the socio-demographic factors associated with postpartum depression.

Method: A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted in Gynecology ward of people's medical hospital nawabshah. Data collected through evaluator administered questionnaires was used to gather determinants of postnatal depression in women and also Edinburgh postpartum depression scale (EPDS) was used to screen the manifestations of postpartum depression.

Results: Among 246 women aged 20–40 years (mean 27.13 ± 4.35), 48.4% experienced postpartum depression (PPD). Demographic factors were mostly not significant, except family type ($\chi^2 = 5.322$, $p = 0.037$), baby's condition ($\chi^2 = 10.617$, $p = 0.005$), and maternal chronic illness ($\chi^2 = 6.301$, $p = 0.012$). Cultural factors such as lack of family emotional support ($\chi^2 = 13.703$, $p = 0.003$) and low awareness of postnatal care ($\chi^2 = 9.926$, $p = 0.019$) were significantly associated with higher depression severity, while breastfeeding encouragement was not ($\chi^2 = 4.300$, $p = 0.231$). Social factors, including low community support ($\chi^2 = 10.088$, $p = 0.018$) and unplanned pregnancy ($\chi^2 = 9.951$, $p = 0.019$), were significant; husband support remained stable ($\chi^2 = 5.958$, $p = 0.114$). Biological factors—hormonal changes ($\chi^2 = 17.850$, $p < 0.001$), preterm birth ($\chi^2 = 13.543$, $p = 0.004$), hypertensive complications ($\chi^2 = 14.520$, $p = 0.002$), and low birth weight ($\chi^2 = 7.876$, $p = 0.049$)—were linked to depression severity. Psychological symptoms—including stress, anxiety, restlessness, bonding difficulty, sleep disturbance, and crying—also increased with severity (p -values 0.001–<0.001). Behavioral factors such as smoking ($p = 0.019$) and junk food intake ($p = 0.001$) were significant, while exercise ($p =$

0.072) and skipping meals ($\chi^2 = 7.068$, $p = 0.070$) were not. These findings indicate that PPD is influenced by a complex interplay of cultural, social, biological, psychological, and lifestyle factors.

Conclusion: The prevalence of postpartum depression in nawabshah was near to past studies, women were Multiparous and financial difficulties, low Education level of husband and mother, husband were unemployed, lives in joint family poor support of community, low exercise, poor sleeping, mothers has high level of stress has been identified main risk factors that cause postpartum depression in women. These findings emphasize the need for early screening, awareness, and psychosocial support to improve maternal well-being and promote healthy mother-infant bonding.

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum depression (PPD) is multiple and severe condition that impacts on many mothers after childbirth involving emotional, physical, and behavioral changes, as well as hormonal changes, the worldwide postpartum depression is 11.9% with rates being slightly higher in low and middle income countries compared to high-income countries¹. Postpartum depression is very big problem in Pakistan, that affects 28-63% of mothers in Pakistan due to various factors² Pakistani women are unsafe to postpartum depression due to cultural and familial factors, including lack of awareness about providing such type of specialized care and emotional support to mother the most important factors that can help to reduce postpartum depression are view to social support, which refers to the feelings of being cared during hard time.³ Postpartum depression is a maternal mental health problem which refers to the emotional, psychological, and social well-being faced by women during and just after childbirth, Which can disturb maternal function and bonding with the infant, The risk factors are categorized into socio-demographic, obstetric, pediatric, lifestyle and psychological groups; Socio-demographic factors include: age, education, income, marital status, low self-esteem, high stress and limited social support, and Obstetric complications are; preterm labour, and unhealthy habits are combine together to the development of postpartum depression also c-section, lack of husband support, and unplanned pregnancy can cause postpartum depression as well as influence on mother and infant bonding⁴. Smoking is very dangerous during pregnancy, a time that already

filled with emotional and physical challenges and also hinder to manage psychological stress which affects on depressive symptoms after childbirth.⁵ Mother's with depression due to poverty, reaching up father dominant society frequently suffer with depression and loss of interest⁶. Postpartum depression is a non-psychotic disorder, that causes feelings such as wanting to harm oneself, having a low sense of self-esteem, feeling guilty for not being able to care for their baby, self-blame, and persistent nervousness.⁷ Between 10% to 20% women experience with depression after giving childbirth⁸. Around 13-19% of new mothers affects which is characterized by a persistent feeling of sadness, low self-worth and hopelessness⁹. The early detection of postpartum depression is important for find out the long-term well-being of both mothers and their children¹⁰. Postpartum depression is the critical time for families, the World health organization (WHO) highlighted that most of the maternal and infant deaths are occurs within the first month after birth, infect half of maternal deaths occurs within the first 24 hours, and 66% within the first week¹¹ Postpartum depression may present as an independent depressive episode or within the bipolar spectrum, especially among women with a previous history of bipolar disorder.¹² Each woman's thought of childbirth are unique, but the definition of a positive and satisfying birth experience differs from person to person.¹³ Some experts say some mothers may experience postpartum depression at any time within the first year after giving the birth.¹⁴ Postpartum depression is very serious and common mental health problem in many mothers, which negatively

effect on mother and their child. Low partner support, low income, suicidal ideation and low self-esteem are major factors related to PPD. So, there is limited case available in Nawabshah. And it is important to explore PPD and its risk factors in mothers also it is important to improving the maternal mental health, ensuring positive mother infant outcomes. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the prevalence of postpartum depression and its determinants in women.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Gynecology Ward of People’s Medical Hospital Nawabshah, a tertiary care facility serving both urban and rural populations. The study was carried out over a period of two months, from 17 November to 17 January, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board. The total sample size was 246 participants. The sample size was calculated using Open Epi Info, with a margin of error of 5%, a confidence level of 95%, and a previous study prevalence of 19.99%.¹⁵ Systematic random sampling was used to select participants from the daily patient list in the gynecology ward. The study population consisted of women

attending the gynecology ward during the study period. The inclusion criteria were: women aged 20 years and above; women within the postpartum period (defined as 0–6 weeks after delivery); those willing to participate and provide informed consent; and those assessed for postpartum depression (PPD) using interviews or a validated self-reported screening instrument, such as the Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale (EPDS). Women who were unwilling to participate were excluded from the study. The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) was developed by Cox et al. in 1978 and later localized by Lee et al. It was used to assess postpartum depression among the participants. The EPDS consists of 10 items that evaluate mood, pleasure, self-blame, anxiety, fear, insomnia, coping ability, sadness, crying, and thoughts of self-harm. Each item is scored on a four-point scale (never = 0, occasionally = 1, frequently = 2, always = 3), with four items scored in reverse. The total score ranges from 0 to 30, with higher scores indicating more severe depressive symptoms.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondent

Figure 2: Prevalence of Postpartum Depression

Table 1: The Association of Demographic Characteristics with Postpartum Depression

Age	DEPRESSION (%)	NO DEPRESSION (%)	X ² /FET	df	P value
20-25	43 (36.1)	56 (44.1)	1.670	2	0.434
26-30	59 (49.6)	54 (42.5)			
31-40	17 (14.3)	17 (13.4)			
Residence					
Urban	44(37.0)	39(30.7)	1.079	1	0.299
Rural	75(63.0)	88(69.3)			
Gender of Infant					
Male	64(53.8)	65(51.2)	0.167	1	0.683
Female	55(46.2)	62(48.8)			
Ethnicity					
Sindhi	77(64.7)	92(72.4)	3.248	3	0.355
Punjabi	24(20.2)	24(18.9)			
Balochi	9(7.6)	7(5.5)			
Hindu	9(7.6)	4(3.1)			
Religion					
Islam	111(93.3)	122(96.1)	0.952	1	0.329
Hindu	8(6.7)	5(3.9)			
Education of Mother					
Illiterate	76(63.9)	78(61.4)	4.701	-	0.480
Primary	18(15.1)	12(9.4)			
Middle	9(7.6)	13(10.2)			
Matriculation	5(4.2)	12(9.4)			
Intermediate	9(7.6)	10(7.9)			
Bachelor of Science	2(1.7)	2(1.6)			
Education of husband					
Illiterate	50(42.0)	62(48.8)	7.480	-	0.184
Primary	16(13.4)	19(15.0)			
Middle	11(9.2)	18(14.2)			
Matriculation	23(19.3)	11(8.7)			
Intermediate	16(13.4)	15(11.8)			
Bachelor of Science	3(2.5)	2(1.6)			
Socio-economic status					
Lower class	95(79.8)	97(76.4)	0.428	1	0.513
Upper class	24(20.2)	30(23.6)			
Occupation level of Husband					
Employed	45(37.8)	47(37.0)	0.017	1	0.896
Unemployed	74(62.2)	80(63.0)			
Occupation level of wife					
House wife	104(87.4)	121(95.3)	5.293	2	0.071
Labor	14(11.8)	5(3.9)			
Employed	1(0.8)	1(0.8)			
Breast feeding					

Yes	94(79.0)	102(80.3)	0.066	1	0.797
No	25(21.0)	25(19.7)			
Mode of delivery					
Vaginal	29(24.4)	32(25.2)	0.023	1	0.881
C- section	90(75.6)	95(74.8)			
Family type					
Single	25(21.0)	14(11.0)	5.322	-	0.037
Joint	94(79.0)	112(88.2)			
Extended	0(0.0)	1(0.8)			
Baby's condition					
Healthy and discharged	78(65.5)	105(82.7)	10.617	-	0.005
Unhealthy and hospitalized	35(29.4)	21(16.5)			
Death	6(5.0)	1(0.8)			
Parity					
Primiparous	33(27.7)	30(23.6)	0.552	2	0.759
Multiparous 1-4	75(63.0)	85(66.9)			
Grand Multiparous > 4	11(9.2)	12(9.4)			
Presence of chronic illness					
Yes	52(43.7)	36(28.3)	6.301	1	0.012
No	67(56.3)	91(71.7)			

TABLE: 2 Association of Postpartum depression with cultural factors.

EPDS	Cultural factors			X ²	df	P value
Do family members provide you emotional support after childbirth?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	13.703	3	0.003
No Depression	29(87.7)	4(12.1)	33 (100.0)			
Mild Depression	102(85.0)	18(15.0)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	60(80.0)	15(20.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	9(50.0)	9(50.0)	18(100.0)			
Total	200(81.3)	46(18.7)	246(100.0)			
In your family is breastfeeding encouraged?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	4.300	3	0.231
No Depression	27(81.8)	6(18.2)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	102(85.0)	18(15.0)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	58(77.3)	17(22.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	12(66.7)	6(33.3)	18(100.0)			
Total	199(80.9)	47(19.1)	246(100.0)			
Are you aware of proper way to provide care after delivery?						

	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	9.926	3	0.019
No Depression	28(84.8)	5(15.2)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	100(83.3)	20(16.7)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	51(68.0)	24(32.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	11(61.1)	7(38.9)	18(100.0)			
Total	190(77.2)	56(22.8)	246(100.0)			

TABLE 3 Association of Postpartum depression with Social Factors.

EPDS	Social Factors			FEX/ χ^2	df	P value
Do you receive any support from your community?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	10.088	3	0.018
No Depression	9(27.3)	24(72.7)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	31(25.8)	89(74.2%)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	10(13.3)	65(86.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	0(0.0)	18(100.0)	18(100.0)			
Total	50(20.3)	196(76.7)	246(100.0)			
Does your husband support you in maternal care?						
No Depression	25(75.8%)	8(24.2)	33(100.0)	5.958	3	0.114
Mild Depression	97(80.0)	23(19.2)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	55(73.3)	20(26.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	10(55.6)	8(44.4)	18(100.0)			
Total	187(76.0)	59(24.0)	246(100.0)			
Was your recent pregnancy planned or unplanned?						
No Depression	20(60.6)	13(39.4)	33(100.0)	9.951	3	0.019
Mild Depression	80(66.7)	40(33.3)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	38(50.7)	37(49.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	6(33.3)	12(66.7)	18(100.0)			
Total	144(58.5)	102(41.5)	246(100.0)			

TABLE 4 Association of Postpartum depression with Biological Factors.

EPDS	Biology Factors			FXT/X ²	df	P value
Have you experienced mood or body changes due to hormonal imbalance?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	17.850	3	0.000
No Depression	23(69.7)	10(30.3)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	99(82.5)	21(17.5)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	72(96.0)	3(4.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	18(100.0)	0(0.0)	18(100.0)			
Total	212(86.2)	34(13.8)	246(100.0)			
Was your baby born before 37 weeks of pregnancy?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	13.543	3	0.004
No Depression	10(30.3)	23(69.7)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	28(23.3)	92(76.7)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	32(42.7)	43(57.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	1(5.6%)	17(94.4%)	18(100.0)			
Total	1(5.6%)	17(94.4%)	18(100.0)			
Did you experience high blood pressure with protein in urine in pregnancy?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	14.520	3	0.002
No Depression	15(45.5)	18(54.5)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	31(25.8)	89(74.2)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	32(42.7)	43(57.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	18(100.0)			
Total	79(32.1)	167(67.9)	246(100.0)			
Was your baby's birth weight less than 2.5kg?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	7.876	3	0.049
No Depression	15(45.5)	18(54.5)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	34(28.6)	86(71.1)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	31(41.3)	44(58.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	18(100.0)			
Total	83(33.7)	163(66.3)	246(100.0)			

TABLE 5 Association of Postpartum depression with Psychological Factors.

EPDS	Psychological Factors			FET/X ²	df	P value
Do you often feel emotionally stressed after childbirth?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	9.500	3	0.023
No Depression	22(66.7)	11(33.3)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	92(76.7)	28(23.3)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	67(89.3)	8(10.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	16(89.9)	2(11.1)	18(100.0)			
Total	197(80.1)	49(19.9)	246(100.0)			
Do you feel that your stress level is higher than usual since delivery?						
No Depression	18(54.5)	15(45.5)	33(100.0)	17.605	-	0.000
Mild Depression	93(77.5)	27(22.5)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	64(85.3)	11(14.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	18(100.0)	0(0.00)	18(100.0)			
Total	193(78.5)	53(21.5)	246(100.0)			
Do you face difficulty bonding or connecting with your baby?						
No Depression	11(33.3)	22(66.7)	33(100.0)	18.940	3	0.000
Mild Depression	53(4.2)	67(55.8)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	48(60.0)	27(36.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	15(83.3)	3(16.7)	18(100.0)			
Total	127(51.6)	119(48.4)	246(100.0)			
Do you experience feeling of anxiety after delivery?						
No Depression	23(69.7)	10(30.3)	33(100.0)	10.740	-	0.012
Mild Depression	86(71.7)	34(28.3)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	62(82.7)	13(17.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	18(100.0)	0(0.0)	18(100.0)			
Total	189(76.8)	57(23.2)	246(100.0)			
Do you often feel restless and unable to relax?						
No Depression	24(72.7)	9(27.3)	33(100.0)			

Mild Depression	81(67.5)	39(32.5)	120(100.0)	10.740	-	0.012
Moderate Depression	63(84.0)	12(16.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	17(94.4)	1(5.6)	18(100.0)			
Total	185(75.2)	61(24.8)	246(100.0)			
Do you have difficulty falling asleep after delivery?						
No Depression	22(66.7)	11(33.3)	33(100.0)	28.048	3	0.000
Mild Depression	69(57.5)	51(42.5)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	67(89.3)	8(10.7)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	17(94.4)	1(5.6)	18(100.0)			
Total	175(71.1)	71(28.9)	246(100.0)			
Do you cry more frequently than usual after childbirth?						
No Depression	15(45.5)	18(54.5)	33(100.0)	16.724	3	0.001
Mild Depression	53(44.2)	67(55.8)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	50(66.7)	25(33.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	15(83.3)	3(16.7)	18(100.0)			
Total	133(54.1)	113(45.9)	246(100.0)			

TABLE 6 Association of Partum depression with Lifestyle Factors.

EPDS	Lifestyle Factors			FXT/X ²	df	P value
Did you smoke during your pregnancy?						
	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	7.760	-	0.019
No Depression	3(9.1)	30(90.9)	33(100.0)			
Mild Depression	1(0.8)	119(99.2)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	0(0.0)	75(100.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	0(0.0)	18(100.0)	18(100.0)			
Total	4(1.6)	242(98.4)	246(100.0)			
Do you exercise regularly during or after pregnancy?						
No Depression	13(39.4)	20(60.6)	33(100.0)	6.926	-	0.072
Mild Depression	23(19.2)	97(80.8)	120(100.0)			

Moderate Depression	18(24.0)	57(76.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	18(100.0)			
Total	56(22.8)	190(77.2)	246(100.0)			
Do you frequently eat any junk food during or after delivery?						
No Depression	16(48.5)	17(51.5)	33(100.0)	16.986	-	0.001
Mild Depression	19(15.8)	101(84.2)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	15(20.0)	60(80.0)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	18(100.0)			
Total	51(20.7)	195(79.3)	246(100.0)			
Do you often skip meals during or after pregnancy?						
No Depression	21(63.6)	21(63.6)	33(100.0)	7.0680	3	0.070
Mild Depression	57(47.5)	57(47.5)	120(100.0)			
Moderate Depression	46(61.3)	46(61.3)	75(100.0)			
Severe Depression	13(72.2)	13(72.2)	18(100.0)			
Total	137(55.7)	109(44.3)	246(100.0)			

Discussion:

The present descriptive cross-sectional study of 246 postpartum women attending a tertiary hospital in Nawabshah found a high prevalence of postpartum depression (PPD) of 48.4% within approximately the first six weeks after birth, which is significantly higher than global pooled estimates of 14% to 17%, reported in large meta-analyses and umbrella reviews.¹⁶ Though, this prevalence is comparable to rates reported from several Asian and other low- and middle-income country settings, where early postpartum, hospital-based studies have predictable prevalence exceeding 30–40%, mainly when EPDS is used as a screening tool.¹⁷ Demographic characteristics such as age, residence, parity, and educational level of mother or husband were not significantly associated with PPD, which is consistent with findings from multiple previous studies and meta-analyses representing that basic demographic variables alone are often weak predictors of postpartum

depression when compared with psychosocial stressors.¹⁸ However, living in a joint family system, having an unhealthy or hospitalized infant, experiencing neonatal death, and maternal chronic illness showed statistically significant associations with depression status, results that support with earlier South Asian and Low and middle countries studies reporting increased depressive symptoms among women facing family-related stress and adverse neonatal outcomes.¹⁹ Cultural factors, particularly lack of family emotional support and poor awareness of postnatal care, were associated with increasing EPDS severity, Similar associations have been consistently reported in previous literature, where inadequate emotional and informational support has been identified as one of the strongest predictors of postpartum depression severity.²⁰ Past studies have exposed that social factors like poor family or partner relationships, lack of support, and unplanned pregnancy are associated

to postpartum depression, the results of this study support these findings, Women with severe depression were least likely to receive support from their community, showing how essential social networks are for maternal mental health, dissimilar previous studies, support from husbands did not differ much across depression levels, which may reflect cultural or contextual differences, In addition, unplanned pregnancies were more common among women with higher depression, confirming that unplanned pregnancy increases the risk of postpartum depressive symptoms.²¹ The observed associations between PPD and biological factors such as perceived hormonal changes, hypertensive complications, preterm birth, and low birth weight are consistent with current understanding of perinatal neuro endocrinology and mirror mechanisms proposed in earlier experimental and clinical studies.²² And Women who reported mood or body changes due to hormonal imbalance had higher depression severity women with, and perinatal depression, severe depression experiencing such changes, behind the idea that hormonal fluctuations play a key role in PPD.²³ Correspondingly, preterm birth and low birth weight were significantly linked with depression severity, consistent with past studies showing that mothers of preterm or low-birth-weight infants are at higher risk of postpartum depressive symptoms.²⁴ As well, hypertensive disorders with proteinuria during pregnancy were associated with higher depression scores, aligning with prior research indicating that pregnancy complications increase vulnerability to PPD.²⁵ The present study established significant associations between postpartum depression and several psychological factors, Women reporting emotional stress after childbirth were more likely to experience higher depression severity, which aligns with previous research showing that elevated postpartum stress increases the risk of depressive symptoms.²⁶ Similarly, mothers who felt their stress levels were higher than usual since delivery were more vulnerable to severe depression, consistent with findings that persistent or elevated stress postpartum is a strong predictor of PPD.²⁷ Difficulty bonding or connecting with the newborn was also strongly

linked to depression severity, supporting past studies that impaired maternal-infant bonding is associated with postpartum depression and may affect child development.²⁸ Postpartum anxiety, restlessness or inability to relax, difficulty falling asleep, and frequent crying were each significantly related to depression severity, in line with prior evidence that these emotional and behavioral symptoms commonly co-occur with PPD.²⁹ The current study found that smoking during pregnancy was significantly associated with postpartum depression, supporting previous research that maternal smoking increases the risk of PPD.³⁰ Regular exercise during or after pregnancy did not show a significant association with depression severity in this study, although prior studies suggest that physical activity may have a protective effect against postpartum depressive symptoms.³¹ Consumption of junk food during or after delivery was significantly associated to depression severity, which is consistent with earlier research signifying that unhealthy dietary patterns can contribute to mood disturbances and increased PPD risk.³² Skipping meals was not significantly associated with depression in this study, though previous studies have highlighted that irregular eating patterns and poor nutrition may exacerbate depressive symptoms during the postpartum period.³³

CONCLUSION

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a significant maternal mental health issue that affects almost half of the mothers in this study, highlighting the vital need for awareness and early intervention. The results exposed that 48.4% of women experienced PPD within six weeks after childbirth, representing a high incidence reliable with other studies in Pakistan and developing countries. Cultural, social, biological, psychological, and lifestyle factors were all found to be associated with postpartum depressive symptoms. Among demographic factors, family type, baby's condition, and presence of chronic illness were significantly linked to PPD, while additional variables such as maternal age, education, and socioeconomic status were not statistically significant. Cultural and social factors, including

emotional support from family, awareness of proper postnatal care, community support, and planned pregnancies, were important determinants of depression severity. Biological factors such as hormonal changes, preterm birth, hypertensive complications, and low birth weight were significantly associated with higher depression scores. Psychological factors, including emotional stress, anxiety, restlessness, difficulty bonding with the infant, and sleep turbulence, were strongly associated with PPD. Among lifestyle factors, smoking during pregnancy and dietary habits were significantly associated with depression severity, whereas exercise was not. Overall, the study emphasizes the multi factorial nature of postpartum depression, showing that both psychosocial support and biological health are critical for mother well-being. Early screening using tools like the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), coupled with suitable counseling, family education, and interventions targeting modifiable lifestyle and social factors, can play a key role in reducing the prevalence and severity of PPD. Addressing these determinants can improve mother mental health, enhance mother-infant bonding, and contribute to better family and community health outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Pan T, Zeng Y, Chai X, Wen Z, Tan X, Sun M. Global Prevalence of Perinatal Depression and Its Determinants Among Rural Women: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Depression and Anxiety*. 2024;2024(1):1882604.
- Sajjad A, Shah S, Abbas G, Aslam A, Randhawa F, Khurram H, et al. Treatment gap and barriers to access mental healthcare among women with postpartum depression symptoms in Pakistan. *PeerJ*. 2024;12:e17711.
- Jamshaid S, Malik NI, Ullah I, Saboor S, Arain F, De Berardis D. Postpartum depression and health: role of perceived social support among Pakistani women. *Diseases*. 2023;11(2):53.
- Sanni SO, Adeoye IA, Bella-Awusah TT, Bello OO. Influence of postpartum depression on maternal-infant bonding and breastfeeding practices among mothers in Abeokuta, Ogun state. *Discover Mental Health*. 2024;4(1):46.
- Knysak K, Maj A, Domosud K, Urban A, Kacperczyk-Bartnik J, Dobrowolska-Redo A, et al. The impact of prenatal smoking on postpartum depression: a systematic review. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*. 2025:1-10.
- Khan S, Ali Y, Riaz A, Khan I, Prem K. Prevalence and Determinants of Depression Among Pregnant Women at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Sindh, Pakistan.
- Melkam M, Fente BM, Negussie YM, Asmare ZA, Asebe HA, Seifu BL, et al. Postpartum depression and associated factors among childbearing women from the recent Demographic and Health Survey data of Mozambique: Multilevel analysis. *Heliyon*. 2025;11(1).
- Puyané M, Subira S, Torres A, Roca A, Garcia-Esteve L, Gelabert E. Personality traits as a risk factor for postpartum depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorders*. 2022;298:577-89.
- Suryawanshi IV O, Pajai S. A comprehensive review on postpartum depression. *Cureus*. 2022;14(12).
- Tzitiridou-Chatzopoulou M, Orovou E, Zournatzidou G, editors. Digital training for nurses and midwives to improve treatment for women with postpartum depression and protect neonates: a dynamic bibliometric review analysis. *Healthcare*; 2024: MDPI.
- Keles MN, Eroğlu K. The use of theory or model in studies on postpartum care: A narrative review. *International Journal of Nursing Knowledge*. 2024;35(1):21-31.
- Mu E, Chiu L, Kulkarni J. Using estrogen and progesterone to treat premenstrual dysphoric disorder, postnatal depression and menopausal depression. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2025;16:1528544.

- Nakić Radoš S, Martinić L, Matijaš M, Brekalo M, Martin CR. The relationship between birth satisfaction, posttraumatic stress disorder and postnatal depression symptoms in Croatian women. *Stress and health*. 2022;38(3):500-8.
- Karkoszka N, Gibula-Tarlowska E, Kotlinska J, Bielenica A, Gawel K, Kedzierska E. Selenium intake and postnatal depression—a short review. *Nutrients*. 2024;16(12):1926.
- Titi I, Ahmead M, Abed Y, El-Sharif N. Prevalence and Risk Factors of Postpartum Depression in Palestinian Women in the Hebron Governorate, Palestine. *Clinical Practice and Epidemiology in Mental Health: CP & EMH*. 2024;20:e17450179338712.
- Liu X, Wang S, Wang G. Prevalence and risk factors of postpartum depression in women: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of clinical nursing*. 2022;31(19-20):2665-77.
- Wang Z, Liu, J., Shuai, H., Cai, Z., Fu, X., Liu, Y., ... & Yang, B. X. (2021). Mapping global prevalence of depression among postpartum women. *Translational psychiatry*, 11(1), 543.
- Khamidullina Z, Marat, A., Muratbekova, S., Mustapayeva, N. M., Chingayeva, G. N., Shepetov, A. M., ... & Aimagambetova, G. (2025). Postpartum Depression Epidemiology, Risk Factors, Diagnosis, and Management: An Appraisal of the Current Knowledge and Future Perspectives. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 14(7), 2418.
- Rahman A, Iqbal Z, Bunn J, Lovel H, Harrington R. Impact of maternal depression on infant nutritional status and illness: a cohort study. *Archives of general psychiatry*. 2004;61(9):946-52.
- Chen Q, Li, W., Xiong, J., & Zheng, X. (2022). Prevalence and risk factors associated with postpartum depression during the COVID-19 pandemic: a literature review and meta-analysis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(4), 2219.
- Werner E, Miller, M., Osborne, L. M., Kuzava, S., & Monk, C. (2015). Preventing postpartum depression: review and recommendations. *Archives of women's mental health*, 18(1), 41-60.
- Alshikh Ahmad H, Alkhatib, A., & Luo, J. (2021). Prevalence and risk factors of postpartum depression in the Middle East: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 21(1), 542.
- Lancaster K, Neale, T., Addison, C., & Kearnes, M. (2025). On Peer Review and Exchanges Unseen: Thank You to Our Reviewers 2023 and 2024. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 50(2), 231-241.
- Vigod SN, Murphy, K. E., Dennis, C. L., Oberlander, T. F., Ray, J. G., Daskalakis, Z. J., & Blumberger, D. M. (2019). Transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS) for depression in pregnancy: A pilot randomized controlled trial. *Brain stimulation*, 12(6), 1475-1483.
- Addo KM. The association between hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and postpartum depression in Ghana: University of West London; 2024.
- O'hara MW, & McCabe, J. E. (2013). Postpartum depression: current status and future directions. *Annual review of clinical psychology*, 9(1), 379-407.
- Liu Y, Zhang L, Guo N, Jiang H. Postpartum depression and postpartum post-traumatic stress disorder: prevalence and associated factors. *BMC psychiatry*. 2021;21(1):487.

- Feldman R, Granat A, Pariente C, Kanety H, Kuint J, Gilboa-Schechtman E. Maternal depression and anxiety across the postpartum year and infant social engagement, fear regulation, and stress reactivity. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. 2009;48(9):919-27.
- Austin EJ, Farrelly, D., Black, C., & Moore, H. (2007). Emotional intelligence, Machiavellianism and emotional manipulation: Does EI have a dark side?. *Personality and individual differences*, 43(1), 179-189.
- Lobstein T, & Baur, L. (2023). The prevention of obesity in children and adolescents. In *Handbook of Obesity-Volume 2* (pp. 28-38). CRC Press.
- Carter EA, Bond, M. J., Wickham, R. E., & Barrera, A. Z. (2019). Perinatal depression among a global sample of Spanish-speaking women: A sequential-process latent growth-curve analysis. *Journal of affective disorders*, 243, 145-152.
- Huang Y, Lu, Y., Huang, Y. M., Wang, M., Ling, W., Sui, Y., & Zhao, H. L. (2020). Obesity in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Metabolism*, 113, 154378.
- Harville E, Xiong X, Buekens P. Disasters and perinatal health: a systematic review. *Obstetrical & gynecological survey*. 2010;65(11):713-28.

